

DIGITAL RESOURCES IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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ABSTRACT

The article examines the requirements for the personal and professional qualities of future specialists imposed by modern society, their development in the process of teaching foreign languages, as well as the use of digital technologies and Internet resources for this. In particular, the importance of a systematic choice of teaching tools to achieve specific goals set by the teacher is shown. In addition to discussing the applicability of using contemporary Internet technologies in foreign language instruction, this article describes the significance and efficacy of using web technologies in foreign language study, both in the classroom and in students' individual assignments.

Keywords: *interactivity, multimodality, content visualization, modern technologies, digital resources, computer technologies, scenarios, awareness, instructional materials.*

Future specialists must possess the skills and abilities necessary to independently acquire knowledge and apply it in practice to solve various problems, collect and analyze facts, make generalizations, and draw well-reasoned conclusions in the era of rapid information technology development [Golubeva,2014]. To succeed, you must be gregarious, collaborate with others in a variety of situations, and seek out ways to resolve conflicts; think critically and creatively, finding ways to solve emerging problems using modern information technologies; and work independently to raise your own cultural level. Active learning technologies help students improve the aforementioned abilities as well as cognitive capabilities during the educational process [Okan,2012].

The attainment of ultimate levels of competency in foreign languages, which were created by the Council of Europe and serve as an efficient pan-European information exchange system, is currently the primary criterion for selecting instructional materials [Ivanova, 2016]. Language learning exercises ought to be engaging, purposeful, and require genuine linguistic innovation. The student will only become a learner, acquire autonomy, and feel motivated to grow in line with the new educational standards in this situation . Today, every aspect of human endeavor,

including research and education, is computerized worldwide. Studying foreign languages has changed dramatically as a result of the growth of the Internet and the appearance of numerous computer tools that streamline the process, making it quicker and simpler to use reliable sources. Computer educational programs have a number of advantages over traditional teaching methods, being, first of all, means of direct audiovisual interactive interaction.

Combining them with conventional teaching techniques in the classroom enables you to train different kinds of speech activities, comprehend the nature of linguistic phenomena, develop linguistic skills, establish communicative scenarios, automate language and speech abilities, and guarantee the application of an individual approach and intensification of the students' independent work. It also helps to boost the students' cognitive activity, motivation, and level of knowledge. Computer communication technologies enable the implementation of techniques in novel ways that stimulate students' creative activities. Computer communication technologies enable the implementation of techniques in novel ways that stimulate students' creative activities. They can collaborate on creative projects with students from different educational institutions and take part in online conversations on a variety of educational websites and topical forums. Therefore, one of the active ways to individualize learning is through the use of contemporary information and communication technology in the classroom [Boldyreva,2013].

Learning benefits greatly from the intrinsic qualities of modern technologies, such as its multimedia, interactivity, multimodality, and content visualization. Therefore, the computer depiction of instructional content, particularly in a joyful, interactive form, benefits students' psychological and emotional states as well as their cognitive styles of thinking, creativity, and mental activity."The use of computer technology introduces heuristic novelty into the learning process and creates motivation for productive self-knowledge and self-improvement, as well as making the lesson attractive and truly modern, learning is individualized, control and summing up are carried out objectively and in a timely manner.[Ryabtseva ,2016]

"What applications or computer programs should be used to achieve the best results?" is a question that teachers frequently consider when considering the use of digital technology for education, according to Tony Prince, academic director at NILE (Norwich Institute for Language Education). "How to use these technologies?" is the next query that comes up. "What are the fastest ways to use different applications?" "How can I use them in class?" "How can I use them for my needs?" "How can I update them?" etc. However, the seemingly fundamental query, "Why do we need to use digital resources?" is rarely posed. It is crucial to remember that, in order to maximize the effectiveness of learning, we must ask "Why" instead of

"How" while considering these issues and start organizing our technology use by establishing our objectives. We will unavoidably come across a vast array of digital resources when pondering the question, "What to use?" Each of these resources has a strong following of supporters who believe it to be the most innovative or effective. Many digital resources that implement the procedures of producing something new or investigating something that currently existing are available online and require installation on a device. These resources can be offered as encyclopedias, tools (Google Docs, Camtasia, Explain Everything), courses (MOOCS, iTunes Courses), and other academic sources (Google Search, Wikipedia, offline dictionaries, Microsoft Office). They can also be used to support research at different stages, including information gathering, synthesis, further supervision of the study process, and working with research results. As well as the process of creation, which includes planning, forming creative groups, and analyzing the completed work. First and foremost, the question of "what to use in the learning process?" presents the biggest challenge when selecting digital technologies and taking into account all of these applications, we frequently fail to recognize the complexity that develop when we employ specific resources directly because we are not aware of how to apply and use them effectively. It's possible that the teacher lacks the time or motivation to thoroughly examine all of the options and guidelines for utilizing the chosen resources. We must first ask the following questions in order to utilize programs and applications as efficiently as possible: "Why? What is the primary goal of integrating computer technology into the classroom?"

The causes could vary: enhance comprehension of the material being studied; encourage students to use educational resources and applications outside of the classroom to extend learning time; - raise the teacher's level of efficiency; - help students become more independent; - help students become more proficient with computer technologies; - help students develop traits like perseverance and tenacity in reaching goals; - help students get ready for the future; - boost student motivation; - reduce the amount of physical resources used, etc. In our planning, for instance, we should take into account materials that will enhance students' comprehension of the subject matter if we wish to increase their comprehension of the material. You must approach this issue from many perspectives in order to do this. Teachers and students now have broad access to professional viewpoints on a wide range of topics thanks to the Internet and other online tools. Because it is impossible to be an expert in every field and because he is frequently too preoccupied with the issues and requirements of his students to evaluate a given topic objectively, a teacher cannot always behave as such an expert. As a result, in order to study a particular issue, one must familiarize oneself with the viewpoint of an expert who has a more comprehensive

and contemporary understanding of the topic under investigation. The instructor can describe what he observed in class by breaking the video up into themed segments. It is feasible to establish the conditions for students to acquire all the skills required to meet the demands of our modern world by using Internet resources in foreign language instruction. In addition to being frequently employed by teachers today, methods of collaborative familiarization with contemporary concepts and trends and their subsequent debate also have a significant motivating impact when teaching foreign languages. Additionally, nearly all students own a computer and other digital devices with Internet access, which makes it much easier for teachers to engage pupils in the process of learning a foreign language online [Akai,2017].

When selecting digital technologies as a teacher, the primary considerations are: what should I use, how should I use it, and—above all—why should I use this or that resource? Prior to implementing computer innovations inside the lesson's framework, it is vital to identify the primary goals and objectives of the lesson itself. Next, we must consider what resources are necessary to best accomplish these aims and objectives, and lastly, how the learning tool we have selected works. Students' participation in the educational process and the development of the skills and abilities required for the successful execution of future professional activities can both be greatly increased by having a thorough awareness of the aforementioned difficulties.

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